

SPEAKING PROBLEMS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY - SULU

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ABSTRACT

The descriptive study examines the difficulties that Mindanao State University-Sulu college students have speaking English. It also discusses the respondents' demographic profiles with regard to gender, age, year level, average monthly income, and educational attainment of the parents, as well as the degree of English language speaking difficulties among MSU Sulu college students in the context of linguistic and psychological factors. It also addresses the notable variations in the degree of English speaking difficulties among MSU-Sulu college students when data are organized by demographic characteristics such as gender, age, year level, average monthly income of parents, and educational attainment of parents; additionally, it addresses the noteworthy association between the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of the degree of English speaking difficulties among MSU-Sulu college students in terms of linguistic and psychological aspects. MSU-Sulu was the site of the study. The study's respondents are MSU Sulu college students who are formally enrolled for the 2023–2024 academic year. The study's respondents were chosen using a purposive sample technique. There are two components to the research tool. The respondents' demographic profile—which includes their gender, age, year level, average monthly income, and level of education—is covered in Part I. Ten statements each on the linguistic and psychological aspects make up Part II. There are five options available, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. It was discovered that the majority of respondents are female, exactly the right age for the year they are in, nearly half of whom are second-year college students, their parents make little money, and they only completed basic education. The respondents concur regarding the degree of linguistic and psychological issues related to their difficulty speaking English. In terms of demographic profile, there is no discernible variation in the speaking difficulties in the English language. The two factors have a moderately high correlation with each other.

KEYWORDS: *Speaking problems, linguistic factors, psychological factors, college students*

INTRODUCTION

The most widely spoken language in the world, English, is spoken everywhere. Despite the lack of an officially designated global language, English is widely used for international communication (Lyons, 2021). Unfortunately, a lot of non-native English speakers have trouble picking up the language.

In the speaking exam at the University of Sought Sumatera, 42% of participants performed well, while 58% did not. Speaking difficulties were divided into a number of categories, including social factors, fluency, grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation hurdles, difficulties accessing English learning opportunities, anxiety and confidence issues, and linguistic barriers (Jaya et al., 2022).

According to Universitas Negeri Manado, the majority of students experienced both linguistic and nonlinguistic speaking difficulties. The three main linguistic issues were mispronunciation, inadequate vocabulary, and poor grammar. The most prevalent language problem was improper grammar. Most said they were unable to correctly compose sentences in English, citing non-linguistic barriers such as shyness and insecurity. The study suggested that the students should study hard and do more practice in speaking (Al Nakhalah, 2016).

Additionally, a study conducted at Zamboanga Peninsula Polytechnic State University found that learners of English frequently have difficulty pronouncing, understanding, and speaking the language, especially when it comes to vocabulary, grammar rules, and pronunciation. Furthermore, students might become disinterested in the language, which would complicate language learning. Interest in and exposure to the target language were the two things that made the language transition process easier. The results of this study will add to the body of knowledge on second language acquisition by highlighting the difficulties and variables that English-speaking students face when learning Filipino. The results will provide educators and curriculum designers with insightful viewpoints to help them create effective teaching strategies, language resources, and support systems that will facilitate English language learners' transitions more smoothly (Reyes et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the researcher continued to see difficulties or issues with college students speaking English in the classroom at Mindanao State University-Sulu. They asked their teachers right away if they could use their colloquial language to explain their topics when they were given reports to write. The majority of college students still lack self-assurance and are hesitant to communicate in English. As a result, the researcher came to the conclusion that the majority of MSU-Sulu college students had trouble speaking English, which made it difficult for them to communicate effectively in English. This issue needs to be addressed.

According to earlier studies, speaking difficulties among English majors have both linguistic and psychological roots. The three categories of linguistic issues are pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary. Fear of making mistakes, shyness, anxiety, lack of confidence, and lack of motivation are examples of psychological issues (Shen & Chiu, 2019). In addressing the difficulties MSU-Sulu college students have speaking English, the researcher discovered that more research is needed to address these issues so that students can recognize and get past the barriers preventing them from effectively expressing and communicating in English. Thus, "Speaking Problems in English Language Among College Students at Mindanao State University-Sulu" was the title of the research study that the researcher carried out.

Research Objectives

The following were the objectives of the study:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of; gender, age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment.
2. To find out the extent of speaking problems in the English Language among College students at MSU-Sulu in terms of; linguistic aspect and psychological aspects.
3. To figure out the significant difference in the extent of speaking problems in the English Language among College students at MSU-Sulu when data are categorized according to each of the following; gender, age, year level, parents average monthly income, and parents Educational Attainment.
4. To explore the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of speaking problems of the English language among college students at MSU-Sulu.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology was provided in this section. The techniques that were employed were as follows:

Research Design

This study used a quantitative approach to gather data regarding MSU-Sulu college students' speaking difficulties with the English language. The researcher specifically used a descriptive survey design. Research that only describes a population's or phenomenon's characteristics was conducted using a descriptive survey design (Talili, 2017).

Research Locale

In particular, the College of Arts and Sciences, the Colleges of Education, Fisheries, Nursing, Public Affairs and Criminology, Business Administration and

Accountancy, and Agriculture were the seven (7) colleges of Mindanao State University-Sulu that were utilized for this research.

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents were one hundred eighteen (118) full-time students from seven MSU-Sulu colleges who were formally enrolled in the 2023–2024 academic year. They were asked to respond to the survey that the researcher had created. Only 118 survey questionnaires could be retrieved, though, by the researcher.

Sampling Design

Purposive sampling was the method used by the researcher to choose the participants. Purposive sampling, which we employed, tries to improve the precision and dependability of data on the sampling selection based on the intended research context. (Campbell et al., 2020)

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher started by composing the letter and then went to the Sulu State College (SSC) Graduate School (GS) dean to get permission to send the letter and survey questionnaire to MSU-Sulu. The researcher then forwarded the letter, mainly to MSU-Sulu's chancellor, requesting permission to carry out the study on campus. At last, the researcher approached the seven deans of the various colleges at MSU-Sulu to request permission to deliver the research questionnaire to the college's student respondents. In addition, the participant received the questionnaire from the researcher along with a brief explanation on how to correctly complete it. Additionally, the researcher allowed participants plenty of time to consider and respond to the statement. After the respondents completed answering the questionnaire's items, the researcher collected the questionnaire from them.

Research Instrument

The researcher took inspiration for the study's survey questionnaire from Rizki et al. (2020) entitled "A survey on speaking problems faced by the second year students of English Department of Universitas Riau". The researcher made the necessary adjustments to make the questionnaire's statements appropriate for both the respondents and the study site. The questionnaire eventually took shape, with the following fields added: name (optional), gender, age, year level, average monthly income of parents, and level of education attained by parents. In the end, the questionnaire took on the following forms: name (optional), gender, age, year level, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment. Finally, there were two sections to the questionnaire: 1. The language elements, including syntax, pronunciation, and vocabulary. 2. Psychological elements, such as timidity, anxiety, and insecurity. Furthermore, each aspect contained a maximum of ten (10) statements.

Validity and Reliability

The Research Survey Questionnaire was modeled after the survey used in the study conducted by Rizki et al. (2020) entitled "A survey on speaking problems faced by the second year students of English Department of Universitas Riau". Hence, the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire are already proven

The survey questionnaire was modified, though, and the researcher submitted it to the Graduate School (GS) office at Sulu State College (SSC) for reliability and validation. Two days later, the researcher finally picked up the questionnaire and the reliability and validation certificate at the GS office.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

In order to measure the data for the first (1) statement of the problem, the researcher used frequency and percentage. The data included the parent's average monthly income, gender, age, year level, and educational attainment of the student respondents.

The researcher used a weighted mean or standard deviation to assess the degree of English language speaking difficulties among college students at MSU-Sulu from both a linguistic and psychological perspective for the second (2) problem statement.

In order to assess the significant difference in the degree of speaking problems in the English language among college students at MSU-Sulu, the researcher used the $t_{\frac{1}{4}}$ test for gender for the problem's number (3) statement. Additionally, an ANOVA was used to analyze the data when it came to age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment.

In order to determine the significant correlation between the subcategories included under the extent of English language speaking problems among MSU-Sulu college students, the researcher used Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation for the problem's fourth statement.

Using the recently updated SPSS app, the researcher was able to compute the data obtained with precision. An expert statistician was also consulted by the researcher for corrections or suggestions regarding the computation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the findings based on the information acquired for this study are covered in this section. It specifically addresses the socio-demographic profiles of the respondents with regard to gender, age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment; the degree of linguistic and psychological speaking problems among college students at MSU-Sulu; the

significant differences in the degree of speaking problems in the English language among college students at MSU-Sulu when data are categorized with respect to each of the following: gender, age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parents educational attainment; and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the degree of speaking problems in the English language among college students at MSU-Sulu.

Gender-specific demographic profile of the respondents

The gender-specific demographic profile of the respondents is displayed in Table 1.1. Just 28 or 23.7% of the respondents are men, while 90 or 76.3% of the respondents are women. The outcome suggests that the majority of respondents were female.

Table 1.1: Respondents' Gender-specific Demographic Profile

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	28	23.7%
Female	90	76.3%
Total	118	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 displays the respondents' demographic profile with regard to age. It was found that only 19 respondents, or 16.1%, were 19 years of age or younger, and that 55 respondents, or 46.6%, were 21 years of age or older. Nearly half of the respondents are young adults, in their early 20s, based on the results.

Table 1.2: Age-Based Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
19 years old and below	19	16.1%
20 years old	44	37.3%
21 years old and above	55	46.6%
Total	118	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of year level. It showed that 54 or 45.8% of the respondents belongs to second year and only 13 or 11% belong to fourth year. The result implies that the second-year students are more than the number of respondents from the other year level.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year Level

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
First Year	41	34.7%
Second Year	54	45.8%

Third Year	10	8.5%
Fourth Year	13	11.0%
Total	118	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of parents' average monthly income. It showed that 54 or 45.8% of the parents earn between P10,000-15,000 Monthly and only 13 or 11.0% earn P25,001 and above every month. The result implies that more than half of the parents are low-income earners.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Average Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
P10,000 and below	41	34.7%
P10,001-15,000	54	45.8%
P15,001-25,000	10	8.5%
P25,001 and above	13	11.0%
Total	118	100%

Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Parents' Educational Attainment

The demographic profile of the respondents concerning the educational attainment of their parents is displayed in Table 1.5. The data indicated that 48 parents, or 40.7%, had completed elementary school, and only 16 parents, or 13.5%, had no formal education. According to the outcome, over 50% of the parents are not highly educated.

Table 1.5 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Level	48	40.7%
High School Level	25	21.2%
College Level	29	24.6%
No Formal Education	16	13.5%
Total	118	100 %

What is the extent of speaking problems in the English language among college students of MSU-Sulu in terms of: 2.1 linguistic aspect and 2.2 psychological aspect?

The degree of linguistically-related speaking difficulties in the English language among MSU-Sulu college students is shown in Table 2.1. The results demonstrated that the respondents expressed agreement or indecision regarding the various claims regarding the degree of speaking difficulties in MSU-Sulu college students' English language learning. They agreed with the following statements: I simply want to talk when

my grammar is correct (mean = 3.949, SD =.690); I frequently struggle to put words together and speak correctly (mean = 3.890, SD =.760); and I usually speak in my mother tongue to avoid misunderstandings (mean = 3.890, SD =.814). Some of the statements for the undecided group are: I feel embarrassed to speak in English because of my poor pronunciation (mean = 3.333, SD =.861), and I am afraid to speak in English due to my limited vocabulary (mean = 3.339, SD =.719). The average mean of 3.613 indicates that MSU Sulu college students are in agreement regarding the degree of linguistically related speaking difficulties in the English language.

The findings merely suggest that MSU Sulu college students have a language proficiency issue when speaking English. According to a study by Amelia and Komariah (2007), the students had a variety of issues, including low participation, inhibition, and mother tongue use. Leaño et al. (2009) also mentioned that indigenous learners have trouble with semantics when speaking. The study concluded that language intervention is necessary to enhance fundamental English semantics skills.

Table 2.1 Extent of Speaking Problem in the English Language among College Students of MSU-Sulu in terms of Linguistic Aspect

Linguistic Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I feel afraid to speak in English because my vocabulary is limited.	3.339	.719	Undecided
2. It feels difficult for me to express ideas verbally when speaking.	3.509	.701	Agree
3. I often get confused to combine and use the proper vocabulary to speak.	3.890	.760	Agree
4. I rarely response to my partner when speaking because they speak faster.	3.390	.785	Undecided
5. I have difficulty arranging the words into sentences to speak in English.	3.641	.863	Agree
6. I just want to speak when I my grammar is correct.	3.949	.690	Agree
7. I have a habit of using mother tongue when speaking to avoid misunderstanding.	3.890	.814	Agree
8. I have difficulty responding to speakers to with various accents.	3.475	1.060	Undecided
9. I have trouble responding to a conversation if the speaker's intonation is not understandable.	3.712	.925	Agree
10. I get ashamed to speak in English because I do not have a good pronunciation.	3.333	.861	Undecided
Average	3.613		Agree

Legend:

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Undecided
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree

The extent of psychological speaking issues in the English language among MSU Sulu college students is shown in Table 2.2. It was evident that the respondents categorized the statements as either agreeing or disagreeing. They indicated that they agreed with the following: I speak English only because my lecturer told me to (mean = 3.924, SD = 1.022); I suddenly lose my train of thought when I try to speak in English (mean = 3.780, SD =.474); and I am less confident in my ability to speak English because I fear my friends will make fun of me (mean = 3.576, SD =.591). Some of the statements made by those who indicated they were undecided were: I would prefer to remain silent because I do not understand what my speaking partners are saying (mean = 3.475, SD =.736), and I do not want to make a mistake because I am afraid of getting corrected (mean = 3.483, SD =.834). The average mean of 3.568 indicates that MSU Sulu college students concur that they have psychological issues related to their English language speaking. The finding suggests that psychological factors prevent MSU Sulu college students from speaking English fluently.

According to Alhaddad (2015) research, anxiety is a real phenomenon that has historically had a detrimental effect on foreign language learners at Palestine University. According to Al Nakhalah's (2016) study, students had a lot of trouble speaking for a variety of reasons, including shyness, anxiety, fear of making mistakes, and a lack of confidence. They are all signs of psychological elements.

Table 2.2 Extent of Speaking Problem in the English Language among College Students of MSU-Sulu in terms of Psychological Aspect

Psychological Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I do not want to make a mistake in speaking because I am afraid of being corrected.	3.483	.834	Undecided
2. I have less confidence to speak English because I think my friends will laugh at me when I speak.	3.576	.591	Agree
3. When I start to speak in English, I get blank and forget everything suddenly.	3.780	.474	Agree
4. I feel ashamed to speak English because I do not have fluent English ability.	3.381	.839	Undecided
5. I feel nervous when I have to speak English with/or in front of other people.	3.390	.654	Undecided
6. I feel anxious when speaking and end up saying nothing.	3.271	.609	Undecided
7. I do not want to speak in English because I am afraid that my partner will not understand what I am saying.	3.551	.674	Agree
8. I do not understand what my speaking partners say so I would rather keep silent.	3.475	.736	Undecided
9. I would rather work alone than work in a team which will force me to speak English.	3.848	.833	Agree
10. I speak English just because my lecturer told me to do so.	3.924	1.022	Agree

Average	3.568	Agree
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Legend:

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50-4.49	Agree
3	2.50-3.49	Undecided
2	1.50-2.49	Disagree
1	1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree

Is there a significant difference in the extent of speaking problems in the English language among college students of MSU - Sulu when data are categorized according to gender, age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment?

The t-test was used because there are only two gender categories. The value of $t = 44.818$ is more significant than the 2-tailed, $p = .05$ tests. It indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. There are no notable differences in the level of difficulty college students at MSU Sulu have speaking English. The results suggest that speaking English is a challenge for all MSU Sulu college students, regardless of gender.

Table 3.1 t-test for Significant Difference in the Extent of Speaking Problems in the English Language among College Students of MSU - Sulu in terms of Gender

	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
					Lower	Upper
Gender	44.818	117	.000	1.763	1.685	1.841

Significant at .05 level

Age, year level, average monthly income, and educational attainment of the parents were all analyzed using ANOVA in Table 3.2. The age f-value of 0.740 is higher than the significance level of .05. The year level f-value of 1.275 is higher than the p-value of .05. The educational attainment of the parents f-value of 0.885 is higher than the significance level of .05. The f-value of 1.052 is likewise higher than the significance level of .05. In terms of age, grade level, average monthly income, and educational attainment of the parents, it can only imply that the null hypothesis is accepted.

When data are grouped by age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment, there is no discernible difference in the severity of speaking problems in English language learning among MSU Sulu college students. The findings suggest that MSU Sulu college students, irrespective of their demographic profiles, are similarly impacted by the lack of statistically significant variations in the severity of their English language speaking difficulties. Furthermore, speaking is essential to human communication, according to (Lawtie, 2007 as cited in Damayanti & Anwar, 2019).

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of Speaking Problems in the English Language among College Students of MSU - Sulu in terms of Age, Year Level, Parent's Average Monthly Income, and Parent's Educational Attainment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age					
Between Groups	1.033	2	.516	.740	.482
Within Groups	80.164	115	.697		
Total	81.197	117			
Year Level					
Between Groups	1.946	3	.649	1.275	.291
Within Groups	58.054	114	.509		
Total	60.000	117			
Parents' Average Monthly Income					
Between Groups	1.848	3	.616	.885	.455
Within Groups	79.349	114	.696		
Total	81.197	117			
Parents' Educational Attainment					
Between Groups	1.401	3	.467	1.052	.397
Within Groups	50.563	114	.444		
Total	51.964	117			

Significant at .05 level

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of speaking problems in English language among college students of MSU-Sulu?

Table 4 shows the significant correlation between the subcategories included in the extent of English language speaking problems among MSU Sulu college students in terms of both linguistic and psychological factors. It was determined that there was a moderate correlation between the linguistic aspect value of $r = 0.417$ and the correlation value of $r = 0.376$. The outcome merely suggests that there is some degree of relationship between the two aspects.

Aftat (2018) highlighted the connection between the fear of criticism and unfavorable assessment and speaking in English. According to Baldwin (2021) as cited in Juhana, one of the more prevalent phobias that students face is speaking in front of others. The feeling of shyness causes their minds to wander or they may forget what to say.

Table 4. Significant Correlation among the Subcategories Subsumed Under the Extent of Speaking Problems in English Language among College Students of MSU-Sulu

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
Linguistic Aspect	Psychological Aspect	.417	.000	118	Moderate
Psychological Aspect	Linguistic Aspect	.376	.000	118	Moderate

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

<0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High;

0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1.0 = Nearly Perfect

Summary of Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

On the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, year level, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment

According to the results, over half of the respondents are 21-year-old females. and older than. The proportion of respondents from other year levels is surpassed by second year college students. Nearly half of the parents only completed elementary school, and the majority make P10,000 or less a month. It suggests that there are more female respondents than male respondents. The majority of respondents are precisely the right age for the year they are in, and the majority of their parents only had access to basic education because they were low-income earners.

On the extent of speaking problems in the English language among college students of MSU- Sulu in the context of linguistic aspect and psychological aspect

The degree of speaking difficulties with the English language in the context of linguistic and psychological factors is acknowledged by MSU-Sulu college students. The findings merely suggest that MSU-Sulu college students face linguistic speaking challenges when speaking English and that psychological factors act as a barrier to English language proficiency.

According to Alhaddad (2015) research, anxiety is a real phenomenon that has historically had a detrimental effect on foreign language learners at Palestine University. According to Al Nakhalah's (2016) study, students had a lot of trouble speaking for a variety of reasons, including shyness, anxiety, fear of making mistakes, and a lack of confidence.

On the significant difference in the extent of speaking problems in the English language among college students of MSU - Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, year level, parents' average monthly income, and parents' educational attainment

Grouping data by gender, age, year level, average monthly income of parents, and educational attainment of parents does not yield significant differences in the degree of speaking difficulties in English language learning among MSU Sulu college students. The findings suggest that MSU Sulu college students, irrespective of their demographic profiles, are similarly impacted by the lack of statistically significant variations in the severity of their English language speaking difficulties. Lawtie (2007) as cited in Damayanti and Anwar (2019) added that speaking is fundamental to human communication.

On the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of speaking problems in English language among college students of MSU-Sulu

The degree of English language speaking difficulties among MSU Sulu college students is categorized into subcategories with a moderate correlation between the linguistic and psychological aspects of the problems. It is simply implied by the result that there is some degree of relationship between the two aspects.

According to Aftat (2018), speaking in English fearfully is associated with the problem of criticism and unfavorable assessment. Baldwin (2021) as cited in Juhana (2012) noted that giving a speech in front of one of the more prevalent phobias that students experience is that of people, and the sensation of being shy causes people to become blank or forget what to say.

Conclusions

The study's conclusions led to the following conclusions:

The majority of MSU-Sulu's female college students were just the right age and year, but their parents were generally uneducated and low-income earners. It only demonstrated that the difficulties MSU Sulu college students are having with the English language is related to linguistic and psychological factors. When data are grouped by gender, age, year level, parent's average monthly income, and parent's educational attainment, there are no differences in the extent of English language speaking problems among MSU Sulu college students. This simply indicates that the demographic profiles of the students are not precise enough to pinpoint the exact cause of the problem.

Recommendations

This research suggests the following:

1. To truly establish whether or not speaking English poorly is a problem shared by all college students, more research on the prevalence of these issues among this demographic is necessary.
2. Future studies on this subject should include variables not included in this study, such as the availability of a speech laboratory, campus policies regarding speaking English at school, and other variables.
3. College students should be continuously encouraged by their teachers to speak English more in the classroom and on campus.
4. College students themselves should make an effort to communicate with one another in English, despite suggestions and criticism for improvement, in order to improve their fluency in the language.
5. It is the responsibility of English teachers to remind their students that speaking English is more important than just learning the verb-subject agreement rules by heart.
6. The administration of the school should make every effort to give the students what they need and motivate them to speak English.

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